

2023.

**5th CROATIAN
NEURORADIOLOGICAL
MEETING**

ZAGREB

December 02-03, 2023

2023.

5th CROATIAN NEURORADIOLOGICAL MEETING

SCIENTIFIC ORGANIZER:

CROATIAN MEDICAL ASSOCIATION

CROATIAN NEURORADIOLOGICAL SOCIETY – DIAGNOSTIC
AND INTERVENTIONAL

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE: DAVID OZRETIĆ, KREŠIMIR DOLIĆ,
MARTINA ŠPERO, ANA TRIPALO BATOŠ, ANA MULDINI
DRAGOJA, VLADIMIR KALOUSEK, IVAN JOVANOVIĆ, BOŽO
ĆURĆIJA

SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE: DAVID OZRETIĆ, MARKO RADOŠ,
GORAN PAVLIŠA, MILAN RADOŠ, SANJA LOVRIĆ KOJUNDŽIĆ,
ANA HRKAĆ PUSTAHIJA, SLAVICA KOVAČIĆ

General information:

Hotel International, Zagreb
Miramarska Cesta 24, 10000, Zagreb

Congress information:

Congress certificate:

The event will be scored by the Croatian Medical Chamber.

Accreditation:

All delegates and guests will receive accreditation with their names on the registration table. The accreditation is an official document and should be carried at all times.

Scientific organizer

Croatian Medical Association
Croatian Neuroradiological Society – Diagnostic and
Interventional

Tehnickal organizer:

FILIDA TRAVEL
Dore Pfanove 7, Zagreb
tatjana@filidatravel.hr
tel: 385 1 4616 522
fax: 385 1 4616 521
www.filidatravel.hr

Authors: Nikola Andjelic, Dusko Kozic, Jelena Ostojic, Aleksandra Ilic, Vojislava Bugarski Ignjatovic, Jasmina Boban

Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Serbia; Department for Radiology Diagnostics, Oncology Institute of Vojvodina, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Serbia; Department for Radiology Diagnostics, Oncology Institute of Vojvodina, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Serbia, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Serbia; Neurology Clinic, Clinical Center of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Serbia, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Serbia; Department for Radiology Diagnostics, Oncology Institute of Vojvodina, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia

Olfactory Dysfunction and Volumetry of Olfactory Bulbs After COVID-19

UVOD: Olfactory dysfunction is one of the most common symptoms of SARS-CoV-2 virus infection. Abnormalities in olfactory bulbs, primarily volume reduction, as observed through imaging, may suggest a central cause.

CILJ: The aim of this study was to compare olfactory bulb volumes in patients with SARS-CoV-2 virus infection, both with and without olfactory dysfunction symptoms, and to correlate these volumes with parameters on the depression scale.

METODE: Ninety patients, aged 18 to 65, were divided into three groups of 30 based on the severity of the acute-phase SARS-CoV-2 virus infection, after completing a questionnaire about olfactory disability. Patients underwent brain MRI 6 to 12 months after the acute infection period. Manual segmentation and volumetry of the olfactory bulbs were performed using the 3D-T1 magnetization-prepared rapid gradient-echo (MPRAGE) and the 3D-T2 sampling perfection with application-optimized contrast using different flip-angle evolutions (SPACE) MRI studies for precise anatomical visualization. Depression and anxiety were assessed using Beck's Depression Inventory II (BDI-II) and the Depression Anxiety and Stress Scale 21 (DASS-21).

REZULTATI: We observed a significant correlation between olfactory bulb volume and reported olfactory dysfunction during the acute phase of infection ($p = 0.048$), where larger volumes were associated with dysfunction. There were no significant differences between right and left bulb volumes in relation to dysfunction ($p = 0.51$ and $p = 0.077$ for the left and right sides, respectively). No correlation was observed between total olfactory bulb volume and depression scores (p -values of 0.643, 0.898, and 0.783 for BDI-II, depression, and anxiety DASS-21 subscales, respectively).

ZAKLJUČAK: Patients who reported olfactory dysfunction symptoms during the acute phase of SARS-CoV-2 infection showed larger olfactory bulb volumes 6 to 12 months later, while there was no observed correlation between bulb volumes and self-assessment depression and anxiety scores. This volume increase might favor neuronal plasticity as a salvage attempt to repair the injury induced by COVID-19 infection. Longitudinal studies are necessary to follow the individual trajectory of neuronal reparation in correlation with patients' symptoms and to clear the findings from this study.